

Mxene as Topological Insulator

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Abstract : Mxenes are 2D inorganic compounds of transition metal carbides, nitrides, or carbonitrides with few atomic thickness. These compounds are exploited for industrial, biomedical, electronic and energy storage devices. Due to their large spin orbit coupling (SOC) and Dirac like band at Fermi level, it is predicted that M'-M"xene (M' and M" are transition metals) can also be used as Topological Insulator (TI). TI is a new state of matter with insulating in bulk and superconducting in surface or edge state. In this paper, we have presented the reviewed literature of the topic and used WIEN2K for Topological Insulating properties of Mxene oxides. We will also discuss briefly about the experimental designs that we are going to perform shortly. We will use Scanning Electron Microscope-Electron Dispersive Spectrometer (SEM-EDS), X-Ray Diffraction Unit (XRD), Scanning Tunneling Microscope (STM), High Resolution Tunneling Electron Microscope (HRTEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer (FTIR) and Angle Resolved Photoemission Spectroscopy (ARPES) for analyzing surface and energy spectrum for abundance, crystal structure, magnetic properties, imaging surfaces at the atomic level, structure & morphology, infrared spectrum and electronic structure of solids, solid surfaces & interfaces respectively. The topological surface state of the mxene systems can also be analyzed with the help of the loop variable called Z_2 invariant and Chern Number. Surface electrons in Topological Insulator are superconducting due to absence of their backscattering. As a result, TI can be used in spintronic devices, transistors without dissipation for quantum computers based on Quantum Spin Hall Effect (QSHE) & Quantum Anomalous Hall Effect (QAHE) and other applications on advanced magnetoelectronic and optoelectronic devices as topological insulator.

Keywords: Mxene, spin orbit coupling, spintronic devices, Z_2 topological invariant and chern number, WIEN2K, ARPES.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is significant effect of dimension and morphology of a material in its electronic, magnetic, optical, mechanical and topological properties. Materials with nanosize, called nanomaterials are studied and applied vigorously these days. Nanomaterials are classified as zero-dimensional (0D), one-dimensional (1D), two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D). 0D nanomaterials include nanocluster and nanodispersions, 1D nanomaterials are with fibre (rod, tube) length from 100 nm to 10 mm, 2D nanomaterials are films (coatings) with nanometer thickness and 3D nanostructured materials is a compact or consolidated (bulk) polycrystal with nanosize grains as shown in Fig 1 (Gusev *et al.*, 2007) below:

Fig 1: Classifications of nanomaterials

Fig 2: 2D nanomaterials

There are several nanomaterials that show dramatic properties in 2D state. The researches on 2D nanomaterials are increasing for their novel applications in the field of physics, chemistry, engineering and biology (Nayak 2016). Some of the typical 2D nanomaterials, like Layered Double Hydroxides (LDHs), Hexagonal Boron Nitride (h-BN), metals, oxides, Boron Phosphate (BP), Transition Metal Dichalcogenides (TMDs), Mxenes, Covalent Organic Frameworks (COFs) and Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) are shown in the Fig 2 above (Azadmanjiri 2016).

Mxene belongs to a new family of 2D Solid Crystals of inorganic compounds similar to graphene having thick layers of transition metal carbides, nitrides and carbonitrides. It was invented by Yury Gogotsi his group at Drexel University, USA in 2011. They have innumerable industrial and biomedical applications.

Ternary metals carbides and/or nitrides and/or carbonitrides are called Mxene, as they are derived from MAX Phase and are structurally analogous to Graphene. They are flexible, more stable, can easily prepared, moldable and exhibit high electrical capacitance. They have layered hexagonal structure (P63/mmc). They have strong vander walls bonding between layers. They are generated from parent MAX Phases ($M_{n+1}AX_n$). The MAX phases are layered, hexagonal carbides and nitrides have the general formula: $M_{n+1}AX_n$, (MAX) where, $n = 1, 2, 3$; M is an early transition metal, A is an A-group (mostly IIIA and IVA, or groups 13 and 14) element and X is either carbon and/or nitrogen (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MAX_phases).

Table 1: List of MAX phases both in thin and bulk form

211 Phases	312 Phases	413 Phases
Ti_2CdC , Sc_2InC , Ti_2AlC , Ti_2GaC , Ti_2InC , Ti_2TiC , V_2AlC , V_2GaC , Cr_2GaC , Ti_2AlN , Ti_2GaN , Ti_2InN , V_2GaN , Cr_2GaN , Ti_2GeC , Ti_2SnC , Ti_2PbC , V_2GeC , Cr_2AlC , Cr_2GeC , V_2PC , V_2AsC , Ti_2SC , Zr_2InC , Zr_2TiC , Nb_2AlC , Nb_2GaC , Nb_2InC , Mo_2GaC , Zr_2InN , Zr_2TiN , Zr_2SnC , Zr_2PbC , Nb_2SnC , Nb_2PC , Nb_2AsC , Zr_2SC , Nb_2SC , Hf_2InC , Hf_2TiC , Ta_2AlC , Ta_2GaC , Hf_2SnC , Hf_2PbC , Hf_2SnN , Hf_2SC , Zr_2AlC	Ti_3AlC_2 , Ti_3GaC_2 , Ti_3InC_2 , V_3AlC_2 , Ti_3SiC_2 , Ti_3GeC_2 , Ti_3SnC_2 , Ta_3AlC_2 , Zr_3AlC_2	Ti_4AlN_3 , V_4AlC_3 , Ti_4GaC_3 , Ti_4SiC_3 , Ti_4GeC_3 , Nb_4AlC_3 , Ta_4AlC_3

Table 2: MAX Periodic Table (Elements in the periodic table that react together to form the MAX phases.)

H	M										A										X										He
Li	Be	Early Transition Metal										Group A Elements										B	C	N	O	F	Ne				
Na	Mg																					Al	Si	P	S	Cl	Ar				
K	Ca	Sc	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	As	Se	Br	kr														
Rb	Sr	Y	Zr	Nb	Mo	Tc	Ru	Rh	Pd	Ag	Cd	In	Sn	Sb	Te	I	Xe														
Cs	Ba	Lu	Hf	Ta	W	Re	Os	Ir	Pt	Au	Hg	Tl	Pb	Bi	Po	At	Rn														
Fr	Ra	Lr	Rf	Fb	Sg	Bh	Hs	Mt	Ds	Rg	Cn	Uut	Fl	Uup	Lv	Uus	Uuo														

Mxene can be synthesized by combustion synthesis, chemical vapor deposition, physical vapor deposition, arc melting, hot isostatic pressing, self-propagating high-temperature synthesis (SHS), reactive sintering, spark plasma sintering, and mechanical alloying. They can be prepared by HF etching. They are hydrophilic due to their hydroxyl or oxygen free surface. ($M_{n+1}AX_n$) after etching becomes $M_{n+1}X_nT_x$, where T is a functional group (O, F, OH), which is removed by the process of sonication as shown in Fig 6. (Naguib *et al.*, 2014).

Mxenes are uses in Energy storage (electrode materials, supercapacitors, reinforcement for composites etc.), water purification membranes, antibacterial biomedical, water desalination, optical nanodevices by controlling of mechanical properties, sensor or capture for different selective gases etc. (Gogosti 2016). They are also used in optical nanodevices by controlling of mechanical properties, sensor or capture for different selective gases. Mxene has been predicted to be a topological insulators applicable in spintronic devices/quantum computing (Liang, 2017) which is mainly focused in this paper.

The major motivation on this material is that the electrochemical optical, electronic and mechanical properties of MXenes can be optimized by selection of parent compound, surface chemistry, and intercalating organic compounds to produce a wide array of novel materials with wide range of applications as above.

As one of its application, Mxene can be used as topological insulator. Topological insulators are the materials that are insulating in their interior or bulk but conductors on their surface. They have large spin orbit coupling (SOC) and Dirac like band at Fermi level. The underlying cause is that their physics is independent of the direction of time i. e. time-reversal symmetry. These surface states are robust or active even in the presence of surface defects (Kane *et al.*, 2005).

When a 2D electron gas is sufficiently cooled and placed in a strong magnetic field, the Hall conductance arises with quantized value, $\sigma_{xy} = n(e^2/h)$ nearly 10^{-9} , called as a topological order. According to the adiabatic theorem in quantum mechanics, “If the Hamiltonian is changed slowly, the system remains in its time dependent ground state.” This is related to the concept of topology that “The properties of space that are preserved or insensitive under continuous/smooth deformations, such as stretching, crumpling and bending, but not tearing or gluing is called topology.” e. g. 2D surfaces in 3D, g is same. Alternatively, e. g. an orange & a bowl with no hole, coffee mug & doughnut with one hole have $g=0$ and $g=1$ respectively. The objects with same number of holes are said to have same topology or homeomorphic. A closed surface is characterized by its genus, $g =$ number of holes and an integer which can be expressed in terms of the Gaussian curvature ‘ $k=1/r^2$ ’ that characterizes the local radii of curvature ‘ r ’ (Golden 2011).

Berry phase has significant role in topology. For a crystalline solid, the parameter space for the Berry phase is the crystal momentum k . The change of the electron wavefunction (u_k) within the unit cell gives a Berry connection, and a Berry curvature, $F = \nabla \times A$, where, $A = u_k | -i \nabla_k | u_k$.

The n in the Hall conductivity*, is an integral of F , and is called the first Chern number (Thouless, et al.,1982) or TKNN/topological invariant. $n=0$ for ordinary insulator and $n \neq 0$ (i.e. $n=1$) for Integer Quantum Hall effect (IQHE) or TI. n remains constant for smooth or adiabatic change and calculated from Gauss Bonnet Theorem (Golden 2011).

The conductivity and the topological order are connected as shown in Fig 3 and 4 below.

Fig 3: Integer quantum hall effect by V. Klitzing (Wiki).

Fig 4: Conductivity increases with no. of holes.

For topologically ordered pure sample with electrons confined in 2D interface between two semiconductors and Lorentz force with k independent Landau levels at Low T High B, “Change in magnetic field changes the Hall conductance in steps as integer multiple of a constant.” In the graph, the increase in the conductance is due to transfer of electrons from bulk to the boundary due to increased magnetic field. i. e. the boundary electrons gives the holographic image of bulk.

The edge states in Integer Quantum Hall Effect (IQHE) are acting as one way conductance channel with chiral symmetry (not superimposable with mirror image) or as 1D chiral wires. The topological invariant exists if we have energy bands that are either full or empty, (i.e., a band insulator) and give the required number of chiral wires on the surface of the system. Then, the surface are said topologically protected. 2D topologically ordered insulating phases can be found beyond quantum Hall systems, in which the spin-orbit coupling plays the role as the magnetic field in the QHE. The edge state occurs at the boundary between a 2D topological insulator and an ordinary insulator (or vacuum) in which spin up and spin down electrons are in IQHE states with opposite effective magnetic field that arises from the spin-orbit coupling. The Chern number n , an integer (from ICQE), doesn't survive in a system only with spin-orbit interaction i. e. without external magnetic field. However, some scholars (Murakami, et al., 2004) proposed a new topological invariant for fermionic systems with time reversal invariance. The invariant is not an integer, but rather a Chern parity which can be either odd or even, called a Z_2 invariant (Kane and Mele, 2005). In a time reversal invariant

electron system where with electric field and without magnetic field, all energy eigenstates come in degenerate pairs called Kramer's pairs. This system is said to be under Time Reversal Symmetry (TRS).

The Z_2 invariant counts the number of Kramer's pairs of edge modes by integrating over half of the Brillouin zone. If the overall Z_2 sum of occupied bands is even, the system is a regular insulator whereas if the sum is odd, it is a topological insulator. e. g. the 2D system graphene possesses two Kramer's pairs, has an even Z_2 and thus is a 'trivial' system, whereas a material with one or three Kramer's pairs would be a topological insulator.

In topological insulators (TI), the spin of electrons (Chen 2012) are controlled. So TI is out of the classification system of conductor, insulator and semiconductor (Konig *et al.*, 2007) (Hasan *et al.*, 2010). The topological classification of materials and the Dirac-like equations (Shen 2013) is possible in Condensed matter physics.

Since the band gap of Graphene is very small due to its weak spin orbit coupling, the prediction of using it as a topological insulator was not much successful. Later, a stable sp-sp² hybrid carbon network was used as its substitute using Dirac cones at low temperature, less than 7 K. This was one of the approaches the use of carbon for new TIs in 2D carbon allotropes (Mingwen *et al.*, 2013). Here, an exotic quantum phenomena was shown in the topological phase transition from trivial insulator to topological insulator modulating with the spin orbit interaction (Xu *et al.*, 2015). Similarly, the CdTe/HgTe/CdTe quantum well (QW) behaves as a 2d TI (Bernevig 2006).

Three-dimensional (3D) TIs are called strong or weak based on four Z_2 invariants ($\nu_0, \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3$). If $\nu_0 = 1$, the material is a strong TI; if $\nu_0 = 0$ and any of the indices (ν_1, ν_2, ν_3) is equal to one, it is a weak TI. In the former case, including the well-known compounds Bi₂Se₃ and Bi₂Te₃, the TRS-protected surface states are present on all facets, while in the latter case, such surface states are present only on certain facets. Their peculiar properties bear the potential for novel types of information processing. Recently, the compound Bi₁₄Rh₃I₉ has been suggested as a weak 3D topological insulator (Ghimire and Richter 2017).

Among the 2D materials shown in Fig 2, Mxene is at the cutting edge of material research. It has been found that Ti₃N₂F₂ is a 2D TI, whereas Zr₃N₂F₂ is a semimetal with nontrivial band topology and can be turned into a 2D TI when the lattice is stretched. It has been found that the tensile strain can convert Hf₃N₂F₂ semiconductor into a 2D TI. Since, Ti is one of the most used transition-metal elements in the synthesized MXenes, we expect that our prediction can advance the future application of MXenes as TI devices (Liang *et al.*, 2017).

The structural, electronic, magnetic, optical, mechanical, electrochemical properties of the following compounds are already being predicted. According to the topological properties of some Mxene oxide and their difference in response with and without application of Spin Orbit Coupling (SOC), the following Mxene oxide are predicted to behave as topological Insulator.

Table 3: List of MAX-phase, Terminated Mxene, Mxene oxide/flouride and Pure Mxene predicted as TI

S. N.	MAX Phase	Mxene with termination	Mxene oxide/flouride	Pure Mxene
1.	Mo ₂ TiAlC ₂	Mo ₂ TiC ₂ T _x (T=O, OH, F)	^c Mo ₂ TiC ₂ O ₂	Mo ₂ TiC ₂
2.	Mo ₂ Ti ₂ AlC ₃	Mo ₂ Ti ₂ C ₃ T _x (T=O, OH, F)	^c Mo ₂ Ti ₂ C ₃ O ₂	Mo ₂ Ti ₂ C ₃
3.	W ₂ TiAlC ₂	W ₂ TiC ₂ T _x (T=O, OH, F)	^c W ₂ TiC ₂ O ₂	W ₂ TiC ₂
4.	W ₂ Ti ₂ AlC ₃	W ₂ Ti ₂ C ₃ T _x (T=O, OH, F)	^c W ₂ Ti ₂ C ₃ O ₂	W ₂ Ti ₂ C ₃
5.	Mo ₂ HfAlC ₂	Mo ₂ HfC ₂ T _x (T=O, OH, F)	^c Mo ₂ HfC ₂ O ₂	Mo ₂ HfC ₂
6.	Mo ₂ Hf ₂ AlC ₃	Mo ₂ Hf ₂ C ₃ T _x (T=O, OH, F)	^c Mo ₂ Hf ₂ C ₃ O ₂	Mo ₂ Hf ₂ C ₃
7.	W ₂ HfAlC ₂	W ₂ HfC ₂ T _x (T=O, OH, F)	^c W ₂ HfC ₂ O ₂	W ₂ HfC ₂
8.	W ₂ Hf ₂ AlC ₃	W ₂ Hf ₂ C ₃ T _x (T=O, OH, F)	^c W ₂ Hf ₂ C ₃ O ₂	W ₂ Hf ₂ C ₃
9.	Mo ₂ ZrAlC ₂	Mo ₂ ZrC ₂ T _x (T=O, OH, F)	^c Mo ₂ ZrC ₂ O ₂	Mo ₂ ZrC ₂

10.	$\text{Mo}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{AlC}_3$	$\text{Mo}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{C}_3\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	${}^c\text{Mo}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{C}_3\text{O}_2$	$\text{Mo}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{C}_3$
11.	W_2ZrAlC_2	$\text{W}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	${}^c\text{W}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$	W_2ZrC_2
12.	$\text{W}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{AlC}_3$	$\text{W}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{C}_3\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	${}^c\text{W}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{C}_3\text{O}_2$	$\text{W}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{C}_3$
13.	W_2AlC	W_2CT_x (T=O, OH, F)	${}^a\text{W}_2\text{CO}_2$	W_2C
14.	Mo_2AlC	Mo_2CT_x (T=O, OH, F)	${}^a\text{Mo}_2\text{CO}_2$	Mo_2C
15.	Cr_2AlC	Cr_2CT_x (T=O, OH, F)	${}^a\text{Cr}_2\text{CO}_2$	Cr_2C
16.	${}^d\text{Ti}_3\text{AlN}_2\text{F}_2$	$\text{Ti}_3\text{N}_2\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	${}^b\text{Ti}_3\text{N}_2\text{F}_2$	Ti_3N_2
17.	$\text{Hf}_3\text{AlN}_2\text{F}_2$	$\text{Hf}_3\text{N}_2\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	${}^b\text{Hf}_3\text{N}_2\text{F}_2$	Hf_3N_2
18.	$\text{Zr}_3\text{AlN}_2\text{F}_2$	$\text{Zr}_3\text{AlN}_2\text{F}_2$ (T=O, OH, F)	${}^b\text{Ti}_3\text{N}_2\text{T}_x$	Zr_3N_2

^aWeng, H., *et. al.* 2015, ^bLiang *et al.*, 2017, ^ckhazaei, M., *et. al.* 2016, ^dIvanovskii, A. L. & Nadezhda I., 1999.

For the state of connection between two conduction band and valance band of topological insulator, we check the following parameters:

- a. **Bulk gap (BG):** We expect small ~300meV band gap
- b. **Cones number(CN):** either the no. of intersection points are odd or even.
- c. **Dirac points (DP):** The intersection of edge states or the crossing points in dispersion graph.
- d. **High Symmetry points:** We observe whether the crossing points goes around those points or not.
- e. **Spin momentum locking:** We observe and measure the spin of the electron and, see whether the spins are opposite (up and down) on either upper or lower cone. The spin is locked with the linear momentum.
- f. **Berry Phase:** The value of Berry phase should be π .
- g. **Z₂ invariant and Chern number:** They can also be obtained by mathematical calculation and tally between two.

The main objectives of the present study is to investigate the topological states of Ordered Double Transition Metal Layered Carbides (ODTMLC) and their oxide form (if able to synthesize them) like $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_2$, $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$, $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3\text{O}_2$ etc.. We will also try the Mxenes with Hf and Zr in place of Ti. Before that, the stable structure of (ODTMLC) should be studied. Similarly, the electronic, magnetic, electrical and rheological properties of the ODLTMC Mxenes will be studied. But this paper will focus mainly on drawing conclusion by reviewing the related literature and topological properties of Oxide Mxene using WIEN2K. The Computational Details of WIEN2K can be found in Blaha *et. al.* 2008. For the detail theoretical review of Mxene, Zheng *et al.* 2011, Kibsgaard, *et. al.* 2012, and for its detail experimental review Jaramillo *et. al.* 2007, Fei *et.al.* 2015, Goodenough & Park 2013, Tarascon 2010, Wessells 2011 are significant.

We are discussing Materials and Methods in section II, Result and discussion of past and present studies on structure, electrical and electronic properties with and without SOC of MAX Phase, terminated Mxene, delaminated Mxene and pure Mxene in section III, Conclusions and outlooks are in section IV, Acknowledgment in section V and References in the last section VI.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

MXenes are more frequently synthesized by **wet-chemical etching** in hydrofluoric acid (HF) or HF-containing or HF-forming etchants, which add surface functionalities O, F, or OH, represented by T_x in this formula as $\text{M}_{n+1}\text{X}_n\text{T}_x$. Etching is required because of strong chemical bonds between A and M elements in MAX phases that make mechanical exfoliation hardly possible.

Fig 6: Wet-chemical etching in hydrofluoric acid

Fig 7: Schematic of MAX (top) to MXene

Other Synthesis Processes are like combustion synthesis, chemical vapor deposition, physical vapor deposition, arc melting, hot isostatic pressing, self-propagating high-temperature synthesis (SHS), reactive sintering, spark plasma sintering (Parajuli 2006, 2007), and mechanical alloying.

A. Computational summary of WIEN2K

We have studied some topological properties of ODTML Mxene oxides using WIEN2K and included in this paper. WIEN2K is a computer program is written in Fortran 90 with Molecular Dynamic type. In the word "WIEN2K", "Wien" is German version of English word "Vienna" where the program was developed and 2K resembles year 2000 of development. Before WIEN2K, there were WIEN93 and WIEN97. It perform quantum mechanical calculations on periodic(unit cell) solids. It uses Full potential (linearized) augmented plane wave and local orbitals [FP-(L)APW+lo] basis set. It solves Kohn-Sham equations of Density functional theory (DFT). The operation system is Linux/Unix. Here, the spin polarized electron is treated as fully relativistic, DFT consider Local Density Approximation (LDA), Generalized Gradient Approximation(GGA), LDA+U, U is Hubbard Potential developed mainly to model high temperature superconductivity, named after John Hubbard, and helps to describe transition between conducting and insulating systems (Blaha *et. al.* 2008).

B. Synthesis and fabrication

Step I: Synthesis of MAX Phases of Mo_2TiAlC_2 , $Mo_2Ti_2AlC_3$

1. The Mo-based MAX phases were synthesized by ball milling Mo, Ti, Al and graphite powders with mesh sizes of -250, -325, -325, and -300, respectively, for 18h using Zirconia (Zr) balls in plastic jars.
2. The Mo/Ti/Al/C molar ratios were 2:1:1.1:2 and 2:2:1.3:2.7 for the Mo_2TiAlC_2 and $Mo_2Ti_2AlC_3$, respectively.
3. Powder mixtures were heated in covered alumina crucibles at 5°C/min to 1600°C and held for 4h under flowing argon.
4. After cooling, the porous compacts were milled using a TiN-coated milling bit and sieved through a 400 mesh sieve producing powders with a particle size <38 μ m or micron.

For 48% aqueous HF solution,

HF 48%: Water 52% i.e. 0.48 parts : 0.52 parts, For 20 ml, HF is $0.48 \times 20 = 9.6$ ml and Water is $0.52 \times 20 = 10.4$ ml, Therefore, 9.6 ml of HF mixed with 10.4 ml of water gives 48% aqueous solution of HF.

Similarly, W_2HfAlC_2 , W_2TiAlC_2 , W_2ZrAlC_2 , Mo_2ZrAlC_2 and Mo_2HfAlC_2 can be synthesized.

Step II: Synthesis of Mo_2TiC_2 or $Mo_2Ti_2C_3$

a) Two grams of Mo_2TiAlC_2 or $Mo_2Ti_2AlC_3$ powders was added, over ≈ 60 s, to 20 ml of 48–51% aqueous HF solution and held at ambient temperature (55°C for $Mo_2Ti_2AlC_3$) for 48 h (90 h for $Mo_2Ti_2AlC_3$) while stirring with a magnetic Teflon coated bar, rotating at 200 rpm.

- b) The mixtures were washed 5 times by adding distilled water, shaking for 1 min, centrifuging at 3500 rpm for 120 s for each cycle and finally decanted (pour from one vessel to another to separate sediments).
- c) After the last centrifugation, the pH of the supernatant (liquid lying over the solid residue after centrifugation) was >6.
- d) The final product was mixed with distilled water and filtered on a membrane.

Similarly, W_2HfC_2 , W_2TiC_2 , W_2ZrC_2 , Mo_2ZrC_2 and Mo_2HfC_2 can be synthesized.

The reaction occurred in the etching process:

C. Characterization and analysis

Scanning Electron Microscope-Electron Dispersive Spectrometer (SEM-EDS), X-Ray Diffraction Unit (XRD) and Rietveld refinement, Electron Spin Resonance Spectrometer (ESRS), Scanning Tunneling Microscope (STM), High Resolution Tunneling Electron Microscope (HRTEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer (FTIR) and Angle Resolved Photoemission Spectroscopy (ARPES) for analysing surface and energy spectrum for abundance, crystal structure, magnetic properties, imaging surfaces at the atomic level, structure & morphology, infrared spectrum and electronic structure of solids, solid surfaces & interfaces respectively. Among them, the brief introduction of the ARPES to be used is described below:

Angle Resolved Photo-emission or Photo-electron Spectroscopy(ARPES)

It is a direct experimental technique to observe the distribution of the electrons (more precisely, the density of single-particle electronic excitation) in the reciprocal space of solids i. e. electronic structure of solids, solid surfaces & interfaces. There is no modeling and give high-resolution information about of both energy and momentum. It has surface-sensitive probe sensitive to “many-body” effects and can be applied to small samples (100 μm x 100 μm x 10 nm). While it is not bulk sensitive, requires clean, atomically flat surfaces in ultra-high vacuum and it cannot be studied as a function of pressure or magnetic field.

Fig 8: Schematic diagram of ARPES

Fig 9: ARPES station on RRCAT, Indore

(Retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Angle-resolved_photoemission_spectroscopy)

ARPES Study in RRCAT, Indore

We are planning to use the ARPES set up by BARC in RRCAT, Indore in Indus 1, Beamline 3 and abroad as an alternative. It was recently modified with CCD based on electron analyzer for PES study of solid samples in angle angle integrated mode. The ARPES consists of a pre-focusing mirror, the monochromator, and a post focusing mirror. The focusing elements are toroidal coated with platinum or zerodur blank whose side view is as shown in Fig 9. The monochromator has a 1.4 meter toroidal grating with three gratings that covers 40-1080A° in vacuum. The experimental station record angle dependent photoelectron spectra of solid samples that can be prepare in situ. Size of the beam spot at the sample is approximately 1mm x1 mm. Flux at the sample is of the order of 10^{10} photons/sec./mm².

The station has both angle integrated as well as angle resolved PES spectra of solid and thin film sample with CCD-MCP based electron analyzer. The analysis chamber (mu-metal) is equipped with a sample manipulator, which is useful to position the sample and record the data at any temperature in the range 300 – 1000 K. The ARPES system also has a twin-anode X-ray source for XPS (ESCA) studies, He discharge lamp for high resolution PES, Ar ion sputter gun, LEED-Auger. The overall experimental energy resolution of the beamline is in the range of 140meV-400meV. A load-lock chamber is attached to the analyzer chamber which enables quick transfer of the sample from atmosphere. The sample size, which can be accommodated on the sample holder, is of area 15 mm² and 0.5mm thickness. The size of the beam spot is about 1mm X 1mm. The samples should be non- volatile and UHV compatible solids for this beamline. The vacuum in analysis chamber is 5×10^{-10} mbar.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Structure of Ordered Double Transition Metal Layered (ODTML) Carbide

The $M'_2M''C_2$ has hexagonal lattice with $P3m1$ group symmetry and five atomic layers of M' -C- M'' -C- M' . M' are the outer layers and M'' the central layers. The carbon atoms are sandwiched between M' and M'' at their octahedral cage. 2D Double ordered transition-metal Layered Carbides are in the form $M'_2M''C_2$ and $M'_2M''_2C_3$ derived from M_3AX_2 phase, where, M comprises M' and M'' that are early transition metals namely Mo, Cr, Ti, Ta, Nb and V. The particle distribution function (PDF) shows that M'' -C layers are sandwiched by the outer M' layers.

Liu *et al.* in 2014 discovered the MAX-phase Cr_2TiAlC_2 with Titanium layer sandwiched between two outer Cr carbide layers in a ordered double Mxene (M_3AX_2) structure (Anasori, B., *et al.* 2015) Similarly, Anasori, B., *et al.* (2015) synthesized the same structured, Mo_2TiAlC_2 , M_3AX_2 phase two families of two dimensional transition metal carbides Mxenes (Hugosson, H. W., *et al.* 1999). With the help of DFT calculation and experimental methods his group studies more than 20 similar Mxenes (Anasori, B., *et al.* 2015). It is found that the $M'_2M''C_2$ Mxene and their O*- or OH*-terminated MXenes have metallic nature that help in conduction of charge.

Fig 10: 2D Double Ordered Transition-Metal Layered Carbides; (Figure from: Anasori, B., *et al.* 2015)

For the existence of this Mxene, the required layers should survive through the etching process from its MAX or parent phase. The schematic diagram of new Mxene structures are as shown in Fig 10. Figure 10 a shows the Mxenes, where, M is any transitional metals. Figure 10 b shows the double transitional metals structures $M'M''$ xene with $M'_2M''C_2$ and $M'_2M''_2C_3$, where M' is the outer layer metal that sandwich the inner layer metal M'' . After the treatment of MAX phase, the resultant Mxene has three terminations namely; O, OH and F (i. e. Oxide, Hydroxide and Flouride) Fig 10c.

The stability of Mxene depends upon the variation of concentration of M'' atom in the middle of the Mxene.

Fig 11: DFT Calculation of the Stability of $M'M''$ Xenes. (Figure retrieved from Anasori, B., et al. 2015.)

The energy difference between fully ordered configuration (starting point) and partially ordered configuration (middle and end point) is as shown in Fig 11a. The figure shows that ordered Mo_2TiC_2 has lowest energy and the total energy varies linearly with decreasing the concentration of Ti atoms in the middle layer. Similarly, the variation of energy difference with the concentration of M'' in the middle layer for the other Mxenes ($M'_2M''C_2$) like Mo_2TiC_2 , Mo_2VC_2 , Mo_2TaC_2 , Mo_2NbC_2 , that are fully ordered at 0K and the Mxenes in their partially ordered state, Nb_2VC_2 , Ta_2TiC_2 , Ta_2VC_2 and Nb_2TiC_2 (some are more stable in partial order) are as shown in Fig 11b. The other ordered mxenes with ($M'_2M''C_2$) are Cr_2TiC_2 , Cr_2VC_2 , Cr_2TaC_2 , Cr_2NbC_2 , Ti_2NbC_2 , Ti_2TaC_2 , V_2TaC_2 and V_2TiC_2 . Likewise, that for the $M'_2M''C_3$ like $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3$, $\text{Mo}_2\text{V}_2\text{C}_3$, $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ta}_2\text{C}_3$, $\text{Mo}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{C}_3$, $\text{Ti}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{C}_3$ and $\text{V}_2\text{Ta}_2\text{C}_3$ are as shown in Fig 11c.

It can be concluded that Lower the value of change in energy, higher the compound is stable. The degree of order is also affected by entropy and/or surface terminations. It is found element on the surface has high energy. However, Mo and Cr prefer to reside on the outer layer, but Ta and Nb in the middle layer.

Table 4. Formation energies (eV/atom) from their elements of select M_3C_2 and M_4C_3 unterminated MXenes

Unterminated Mxenes	Formation energy (eV/atom) transition metal (M)					
	Ti	V	Nb	Ta	Cr	Mo
M_3C_2	-0.365	-0.254	0.039	-0.017	0.012	0.328
M_4C_3	-0.594	-0.582	-0.236	-0.259	-0.092	0.258

For ordering, a driving force is necessary which is calculated as shown in Table 4. It shows that the Mo_3C_2 and Mo_4C_3 are highly unstable and cannot be synthesized. In this case, an important point to note is that the bond between Molybdenum and Carbon atoms are not stacking in FCC arrangement of Mxene layers (Table 4. Anasori, B., et al. 2015).

If another element like Ti is added, Mo rejects FCC arrangement with C and form Mo_2TiC_2 or $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3$ that are hexagonal in structure. Moreover, the same happens in case of Chromium and it reside in the outer layer of Mxene.

B. XRD patterns of different phases of MXene synthesis

We can use X-ray diffraction (XRD) to check the structure at precursor MAX Phase (lower red pattern), and after etching and delamination (middle green and top blue patterns respectively) as shown in Fig 12. The figure shows that the (001) peaks of $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ were replaces all the peaks of $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$ and the c-lattice parameter (c-LP) or interlayer spacing is increases from 18.6 \AA to 25.8 \AA and 36.1 \AA of the etched and delaminated mxene Mo_2TiC_2 respectively due to presence of intercalated water and cations between the Mxene sheet.

As a result, the peaks are broadened and shifted down to lower angles and hence due to domain size reduction along [001] in etching process. The c-LP increases further in delaminated process due to the same reason as above. In the Fig 12, [110] peak around 62° , present after etching disappears after delamination shows that etching alone doesnot break the Mxene flakes stacking along non-basal directions. While the disappearance of this peak after delamination shows that the vacuum filtration is haphazard but still the crystallographic order along the direction [001] is preserved.

Fig 12: XRD patterns of $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$ before (red) and after (green) HF treatment and after delamination (blue). (Figure retrieved from Anasori, B., et al. 2015.)

C. Crystal structure and Lattice parameters of MAX-phase, Mxene and Mxene Oxides

In general, the crystal structure of MAX Phase and terminated Mxene after etching is $P6_3/mmc$ with hexagonal structure with space group number 194; that for Mxene oxide is $P1$ with triclinic structure and space group number 1 (SI Khazaei, M., 2016) and for Mxene same as its MAX phase.

For Mo_2TiC_2 , the Mo, Ti, C atoms are sitting at $(2/3, 1/3, z)$, $(0, 0, 1/2)$, and $(1/3, 2/3, z)$, respectively, whereas for $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3$, the Mo, Ti, C₁ and C₂ atoms are sitting at $(0, 0, z)$, $(2/3, 1/3, z)$, $(0, 0, 0)$ and $(1/3, 2/3, z)$, respectively. The space-group is $P6_3/mmc$; the c-lattice parameters for both MXenes were calculated from the location of the (001) peaks in the irrespective XRD pattern (SI Anasori, B., et.al. 2015). The surface termination species O/F are sitting at $(0, 0, z)$.

$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$ belongs to $P6_3/mmc$ and there are 12 atoms in one unit cell, the individual coordinate is: $(2/3, 1/3, u)$ of Mo, $(0, 0, 0)$ of Ti, $(0, 0, 1/4)$ of Al, $(1/3, 2/3, 5v)$ of C. The stable geometry parameters are obtained using the usual optimization procedure of hexagonal cell: $a=b=3.0157 \text{ \AA}$, $c=18.6032 \text{ \AA}$, $u=0.1352$, $v=0.0677$, consistent with the experimental data, $a=b=2.997 \text{ \AA}$, $c=18.6608 \text{ \AA}$, $u=0.13336$, $v=0.0687$. For $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$; $a=b=2.9357 \text{ \AA}$, $c=36.1 \text{ \AA}$ $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3\text{T}_x$; $a=b=2.9598 \text{ \AA}$, $c=45.5 \text{ \AA}$.

D. Atomic Structure of Ordered Double Transition Metal Layered (ODTML) Carbide Oxides

For the functionalization of Mxene, two oxygen atoms are required in each cell that can be adsorbed on the top or the hollow sites of the transitional metals. With respect to their energy the calculation shows that they are adsorbed on the top of the hollow sites of the surfaces after structural optimization (Khazaei et al. 2013, Khazaei et al. 2014). In fig 13, the unit vectors in ab plane are denoted by black arrows. There are two types of hollow sites on Mxene depending upon whether the carbon atom is or is not under the hollow, say X or Y respectively. In this way, three different configuration exist for terminations of $\text{M}'_2\text{M}''\text{C}_2$: XX, XY and YY. In XX(YY) model the two oxygen atoms are adsorbed on the top of X(Y) hollow sites in XX (YY) model and one on X site & other on Y site in XY model.

Fig 13: Top (left panels) and side (right panels) views of two-dimensional (a) $\text{M}'_2\text{M}''\text{C}_2$ and (b) $\text{M}'_2\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$ MXenes.

Fig 14 a: Phonon dispersions for $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$ and $\text{W}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$. Reprinted with permission from Khazaei, M. ©2016 APS.

Fig 14 b: Phonon dispersions for $\text{Mo}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$, $\text{Mo}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$, $\text{W}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$ and $\text{W}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$. Reprinted with permission from Khazaei, M. ©2016 American Physical Society.

Table 5: The total energy in eV per unit cell of the optimized XX, XY and YY model for the six $\text{M}_2'\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$

Mxene Oxide/ Hollow Sites	XX	XY	YY
$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$	-64.057	-64.628	-65.238
$\text{Mo}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$	-64.436	-64.868	-65.388
$\text{Mo}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$	-66.278	-66.765	-67.328
$\text{W}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$	-68.336	-68.911	-69.588
$\text{W}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$	-68.769	-69.187	-69.747
$\text{W}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$	-70.571	-71.075	-71.694

The most stable model structure is obtained after full optimization as in the table above. It is clear from the table that the lowest energy is obtained in YY model which is suitable structure for $\text{M}_2'\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$ is shown in fig 10 b. The energy formation differ by the occupation of middle single or double M'' site of single and double layered Mxene by M' outer layer atoms. Net charges of atoms in $\text{M}'_2\text{M}''\text{C}_2$ are found to be -0.66 for M' , -0.76 for M'' and -1.47 for C respectively (SI Anasori, B., et.al. 2015).

The phonon dispersion relation helps to examine whether all the atoms in $\text{M}_2'\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$ are in equilibrium position or not. The relation for $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$ and $\text{W}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$ are shown in Fig 11 above. If all the phonon modes are positive i. e. above zero, the structure is stable which is clearly shown in Fig 11. The highest frequency of $\text{M}_2'\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$ (780cm^{-1}) is higher than MoS_2 (475cm^{-1}) and lower than that of graphene (1600cm^{-1}) indicates that the Mxene is more stable than MoS_2 and less stable than graphene. The study of Ion adsorption energies shows that $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$ and $\text{Mo}_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$ are more reactive than $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$ (SI Anasori, B., et.al. 2015).

E. Electrical & Electronic properties measurement of terminated Double Ordered Mxene

For electrical property, DC transport measurement was performed in Quantum Design Physical Property Measurement System (QDPPMS) and equipped with an external Kithley current source and nanovoltmeter. Two types of samples were characterized: i) Multilayer samples, where, Mxene powder is uniaxially pressed to 1 GPa to make thin discs < 0.5 mm thick and ii) d-Mxene films that were made by filtration and were strong enough for their resistivity to be measured directly.

A four probe geometry with silver paint(for electrical contacts) was used, for the transport properties. Magnetic Field Dependent Magnetoresistance (MFDMR) on the multilayered $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ disks was measured with magnetic field of upto $\pm 5\text{T}$ applied out of the plane of the samples.

In order to know the electronic properties, the total density of states of $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ are plotted. The figure 15 (a-c) shows the total and projected densities of states for OH-, O-, and F-terminated Mo_2TiC_2 . In the figure, there is larger contribution of Mo-Mo d orbitals unlike Ti orbitals in Mo_2TiC_2 .

Figure 15 (a-c). Electronic structures of selected Double Ordered MXenes. (Figure retrieved from Anasori, B., et al. 2015.)

F. Electronic Structures of Double Ordered Mxene Oxide

It has been theoretically predicted that some of the ordered layered double transition metal carbide oxides $\text{M}'_2\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$ ($\text{M}' = \text{Mo}, \text{W}; \text{M}'' = \text{Ti}, \text{Zr}, \text{Hf}$) also behaves as topological insulators. Their Z_2 invariant can be calculated with the help of parities (of the occupied bands below the fermi level at time reversal invariant momenta) and also by the presence of edge states. It has been found that the mxene oxide shows non trivial gap in the range of 0.041-0.285 eV in GGA and 0.119-0.409 eV in hybrid functional (HSE06). The band gap is due to spin-orbit coupling between the degenerate states $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and d_{xy} of M' and M'' . Consequently, the band inversion occurs at Γ point among the degenerate $d_{x^2-y^2}/d_{xy}$ orbitals and a nondegenerate $d_{3z^2-r^2}$ orbitals due to hybridization of neighboring orbitals. The structural stability was shown with the help of phonon dispersion calculation. The heavy transitional metal like W-based Mxenes have high band gap and are found to be more applicable as topological insulators in room temperature. The electronic structure of $\text{M}'_2\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$ shows that they are nontrivial topological semimetals, while, the pristine are metallic (Anasori, B., et al. 2016) while upon proper surface functionalization, $\text{M}'_2\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ shows semiconductors like behavior. (Anasori, B., et al. 2016; Khazaei, M., et al. 2013). In this study, the structural properties of $\text{M}'_2\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{O}_2$ are studied thoroughly. The band structure is more or less same among all the double-layer mxene oxides under consideration. The electronic band structure of different ODTML Mxene Oxides with and without SOC are taken under consideration as shown in Fig 16 below:

$\text{W}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$ w/o SOC	$\text{W}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$ w/o SOC	$\text{W}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$ w/o SOC	$\text{Mo}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$ w/o SOC	$\text{Mo}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$ w/o SOC	$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$ w/o SOC
$\text{W}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$ w SOC	$\text{W}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$ w SOC	$\text{W}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$ w SOC	$\text{Mo}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$ w SOC	$\text{Mo}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$ w SOC	$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$ w SOC

Fig 16: Electronic band structure of ODTML Mxene Oxides with and without SOC (w-with, w/o-without)

In the figure, the Fermi energy is at 0 eV. Without the application of SOC, the lowest of Conduction Band (CB) and highest of Valence Band (VB) touch only at one Γ point, the system is metallic. From the projected band structures, the band near the Fermi energy originates from d orbitals of transition metals M' and M'' . In hexagonal crystal structure the d orbitals are classified in three groups; (d_{xy} , $d_{x^2-y^2}$), (d_{xz} , d_{yz}), $d_{3z^2-r^2}$ and p orbitals are divided into two groups; (p_x , p_y) and p_z . More precisely, d_{xy} and $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals of transition metals M' and M'' dominates the regions in between CB and VB around Γ point.

Normally, the heavy elements material in 2D form connected at Fermi level like in the above case can be topological insulator. For assurance, the Non-trivial Band Topology Test is performed with Spin Orbit Coupling (SOC). Due to SOC, the Topmost valence band and lowest conduction band are degenerated at Fermi Level, get lifted and open the band gap. As a result, the $M_2'M''C_2O_2$ Mxenes ($M' = Mo, W$; $M'' = Ti, Zr, Hf$) becomes semiconductor with indirect band gap as in the following table:

Table 5: Comparison of band gap obtained from WIEN2K with that from VASP/QE/HSE06 after SOC

Mxene Oxide	SOC for all elements VASP/QE/HSE06	SOC only for M'	SOC only for M''	WIEN2K
$Mo_2TiC_2O_2$	0.041/0.036/0.119	0.027	0.009	0.129
$Mo_2ZrC_2O_2$	0.069/0.065/0.125	0.026	0.039	0.135
$Mo_2HfC_2O_2$	0.153/0.151/0.238	0.027	0.120	0.248
$W_2TiC_2O_2$	0.136/0.135/0.290	0.121	0.010	0.295
$W_2ZrC_2O_2$	0.170/0.166/0.280	0.123	0.040	0.290
$W_2HfC_2O_2$	0.285/0.285/0.409	0.135	0.140	0.419

It is found that the resultant band gap increases with the increase in SOC of M' and M'' . It is 0.285 eV for $W_2HfC_2O_2$ and 0.041 eV for $Mo_2TiC_2O_2$. The results from WIEN2K is slightly more than that from VASP/QE/HSE06. It shows that SOC can open band gap. The table 5 shows that the SOC for each transitional metal opens gap as large as ~ 0.026 , ~ 0.123 , ~ 0.01 , ~ 0.04 , and ~ 0.14 eV for Mo, W, Ti, Zr, and Hf, respectively. HSE06 is better than GGA for band gap. The band gaps are found to be in the range 0.119–0.409 eV by using HSE06 and 0.129–0.419 using WIEN2K and are same.

After SOC, the Z_2 topological invariant is calculated for nontrivial topological property by calculating the parity of their Valence Band Wavefunctions at the time reversal invariant momentum (TRIM) points of Brillouin Zone (Fu, Kane & Mele, 2007)(Fu & Kane 2007). In details, the Z_2 index ν is calculated as $(-1)^\nu = \prod \delta(k_i)$ where $\delta(k_i) = \prod \zeta_n^i (= \pm 1)$ is the parity of the n^{th} valence band at the i^{th} TRIM k_i , and N is the total number of the occupied valence bands (Fu, Kane & Mele, 2007)(Fu & Kane 2007). If $\nu = 0$, it is trivial and if $\nu = 1$, it is non trivial topological phase respectively. Since the crystal structure of double-layer Mxene oxide is hexagonal, the TRIM points are at Γ point: point: $k = (0,0)$, M_1 point: $k = (0,0.5)$, M_2 point: $k = (0.5,0)$, and M_3 point: $k = (0.5,0.5)$. In hexagonal symmetry, the parities at M_1 , M_2 , and M_3 are same and can be denoted simply by M . Then, $(-1)^\nu$

$= \delta^3(M)\delta(\Gamma)$. the parity analysis of the occupied bands at TRIM points gives $=1$. So, $M_2'M''C_2O_2$ ($M'= Mo, W; M''= Ti, Zr, Hf$) MXenes are TIs. Another significant evidence for $M_2'M''C_2O_2$ as TI is the odd number of topologically conducting edge states crossing the Fermi energy.

Similarly, the electronic bands of $Mo_2TiC_2O_2$ and $W_2HfC_2O_2$ near the Fermi energy are mainly composed of $d_{x^2-y^2}$, d_{xy} , and $d_{3z^2-r^2}$ orbitals of transition metals M' and M'' that helps to construct the tight binding hamiltonian based on Maximally Localized Wannier Functions. The band structure calculation of the nanoribbon structures of $Mo_2TiC_2O_2$ and $W_2HfC_2O_2$ shows three and one times crossing the Fermi energy along Γ -M points.

In case of $M_2'M''C_2O_2$, the band is already inverted before SOC. So, SOC has only contribution in to open the band gap as shown in Fig 17. For more details, the lattice constant is gradually increased from its optimized value(a_0), resulting energy gap are noted and the band structure are plotted respectively. It is found that when lattice constant is very large $>1.2 a_0$ and SOC is absent, $W_2HfC_2O_2$ is a trivial band insulator in which two top most valence band made of bonding and non bonding states of $d_{3z^2-r^2}$ orbitals with even and odd parities, respectively, while the lowest CB are doubly degenerated and are formed by bonding state of $d_{xy}/d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals with even parity.

Fig 17: Band structure of $W_2HfC_2O_2$ projected onto d orbitals of W and Hf atoms; (w-with, w/o-without)

As the lattice constant is reduced, the hybridization between neighbouring d orbitals increases and hence the bonding doubly degenerate $d_{xy}/d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals shift downward below the fermi level and nonbonding state of $d_{3z^2-r^2}$ moves above the fermi level resulting band inversion. As the $d_{xy}/d_{x^2-y^2}$ remains exactly at fermi level the system is semimetallic. With SOC, the finite band gap is induced as shown in Fig 18. and the system becomes non trivial insulator.

The similar phenomenon is observed in other Mo_2CO_2 and W_2CO_2 (H. Weng *et al.* 2015), $ZrTe_5$, WS_2 etc. Similarly, we can show the non trivial topology of $M_2'M_2''C_3O_2$ ($M' = Mo, W; M''= Ti, Zr, Hf$).

Fig 18: Evolution of electronic bands at the Γ points

The Fig 18 shows the evolution of electronic bands at the Γ points with respect to the lattice towards its optimized value a_0 . It shows that the band inversion was occurred before the application of SOC & there is large contribution of d orbital in W based Mxene.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOKS:

Recently discovered ordered double transition metal layered carbide with one or two layers of a transition metal (e. g., Ti) are sandwiched between the layers of another one (e. g., Mo) in a 2D carbide structure. The **electronic properties** of the Mxene can be changed from **metallic to semiconductor like** by changing the two outer transition metal layers of the 2D carbide or simply in atomic level. In addition, spin polarized DFT calculation shows 0.05eV band gap in the Mo containing Mxene. They were

confirmed by their temperature dependent conductivity and magnetoresistance. This is quite different and efficient from previous methods for tuning electronic and electrochemical properties like doping, phase change, or surface functionalization.

The stability of recently predicted ordered double transition-metal layered carbides at absolute zero are on two tendencies. One is the Mo and Cr atoms, that donot crystallize in rock salt structure, are on the outside, they control the 2D flakes chemical and electrochemical properties, while other is Nb and Ta, that prefer middle layer. Their stability is effected under different entropy and surface terminations. It has been found that the electrochemical properties of $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ is dominated by the surface Mo layer. The similar behavior is expected from nitrides and carbonitrides compounds. Moreover, mxene have tubes where placing smaller atom in the inner layer will decrease strain and stress, increasing nanotube stability. All these phenomena shows that more and more members of Mxene are possible (Enyashin, A. *et.al.* 2012).

We have studied the stable structure of Ordered Double Layered Transition Metal Carbides (ODTMLC) $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$, $\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3$ and $\text{Cr}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ (Mxenes) using Wien2K, the electronic and electrical properties of the ODTMLC Mxenes in brief and the topological states of the ODTMLC Mxenes.

We have found theoretically that the oxides of some recently synthesized ODTMLC are topological insulators. Among them, $\text{W}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$ has largest band gap of 0.285 eV resulted from SOC in transition-metal M' and M'' . As the continuation of this work, we will check it experimentally.

Finally, Mxenes are chemically and mechanically stable due to their ceramic nature. They can be found in monolayer, few layer and multilayer. They can be synthesized as a mixture of light and heavy element that helps the number of valence and relativistic SOC tunable. The thickness of the Mxene can be controlled to know the quantum confinement phenomena. Their surface with different functional groups helps in surface state engineering. More than 18 Mxene are predicted to be used as topological insulators. Some of these Chromium based Mxene oxide and nitrogen based ODTML Mxene can be investigated theoretically in the next step and The synthesis of respective Mxene oxides for the experimental verification of their TI properties is our immediate challenge.

S. N.	MAX Phase	Mxene with termination	Mxene oxide/flouride	Pure Mxene
1.	$\text{Cr}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$	$\text{Cr}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	$\text{Cr}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{O}_2$	Cr_2TiC_2
2.	$\text{Cr}_2\text{TiAlC}_3$	$\text{Cr}_2\text{TiC}_3\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3\text{O}_2$	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3$
3.	$\text{Cr}_2\text{HfAlC}_2$	$\text{Cr}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	$\text{Cr}_2\text{HfC}_2\text{O}_2$	Cr_2HfC_2
4.	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Hf}_2\text{AlC}_3$	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Hf}_2\text{C}_3\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Hf}_2\text{C}_3\text{O}_2$	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Hf}_2\text{C}_3$
5.	$\text{Cr}_2\text{ZrAlC}_2$	$\text{Cr}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	$\text{Cr}_2\text{ZrC}_2\text{O}_2$	Cr_2ZrC_2
6.	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{AlC}_3$	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{C}_3\text{T}_x$ (T=O, OH, F)	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{C}_3\text{O}_2$	$\text{Cr}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{C}_3$

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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